

**Does “Going Green”
Promote Global Value Chains Integration?**

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Abstract

Many business entities still prioritize profits over environmental protection and perceive these two goals as inherently incompatible. Thus, this study examines the impact of environmentally oriented investments on the firms’ integration into global value chains (GVCs). Using firm-level data in 41 countries from the Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS), we show that firms could raise their opportunity to participate in GVCs by adopting environment protection actions through the mediation of productivity gains, yet the impact of adopting such actions on the intensity of GVC participation tends to be negligible. Likewise, larger firms are more likely to experience a raise of their chance to participate in international trade through environmental upgrading rather than their smaller counterparts. This finding is important since firms are increasingly being held accountable for their significant contribution in the environment degradation.

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1. Introduction

The World Trade Organization (WTO)'s commitment « ... *to the protection and preservation of the environment through its objective of ensuring sustainable development ...* » highlights the rising awareness of environmental concerns in the present-day globalized world. Indeed, environmental protection goals have become one of the top priorities on the global agenda, as environmental protection is crucial for combating climate change. Likewise, they represent a critical component of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as several of the SDGs aim to ensure a sustainable use of natural resources and reduce the risk of resource depletion and environmental degradation (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). This topic becomes even more important with the increasing participation of developing countries into global value chains (GVC) that represent nearly 70% of the current trade flows, according to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). Such flows within GVCs might contribute to the increase in CO₂ emissions (Bazillier et al., 2023). However, with more stringent environmental regulations at the national and international levels, adopting green tools might increase the likelihood of firms to integrate GVC. Indeed, such firms must be able to compete internationally and abide by different environmental standards. Thus, this paper aims to examine the nexus between improving firms' environmental performance and GVC integration.

Being increasingly being held accountable for their significant contribution in the environment degradation, upgrading firms' environmental performance is crucial for achieving environmental sustainability. This will help them mitigate the negative footprint of their production operations. Nevertheless, the idea that the quest for profits and the quest for sustainability are opposing forces has been a long-standing belief among many business entities. More particularly, the assumption is that firms prioritize profits over the environment's protection, and that these two goals are inherently incompatible. However, this view has been challenged in recent years, as a growing body of research suggests that businesses may be able to reap a range of long-term benefits on account of the adoption of green strategies. The existing literature confirms that the adoption of environment protection actions does not only generate social benefits as the reduction of pollution for instance but also generates benefits specific to the firm as productivity gains and performance upgrading (Berman and Bui, 2001, Delmas and Pekovic, 2012 and Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2013).

Nevertheless, less attention was attributed to the impact of the firm's environmental performance on its ability to participate in international trade. In light of the zero net emissions scenarios, gaining access to foreign markets represents one of the primary motivations for the firms to adopt control measures that mitigate the environmental impact of their production operations (Achabou et al., 2015). In this line of thought, a strand of the literature (country-specific) shows a positive significant effect of the adoption of environmentally oriented investments on the firm's export performance (Alpay et al., 2001, Galdeano-Gómez, 2010 and Antonietti and Marzucchi, 2013). Another strand of the literature analyzes the impact of GVC participation on environmental performance (Agostino et al, 2023 and Siewers et al, 2023), this paper tends to fill the gap by examining the impact of firms' environmental performance improvements on the integration in global value chains (GVCs). These studies find that firms that enter GVCs perform better across several environmental indicators, showing to what extent global supply chains can go hand in hand with greener production.

Against this background, this paper draws its significance from the acknowledgment of the importance of firms' collaboration on the environmental protection initiatives, as environmental

sustainability cannot be solely achieved through regulatory frameworks. Therefore, it is important to contest the conventional notion of the trade-off between environment protection and private benefits, in an attempt to motivate the firms' involvement in green investments. This perspective, widely known as the Porter Hypothesis (PH), suggests that compliance to environmental regulations, even if it imposes additional costs on firms, can serve as a driving force for investment in innovative and clean production technologies that may lead to productivity gains, enhancing the firm's competitiveness on the market (Porter and Linde, 1995 and Ramzy and Zaki, 2018). To do so, we use firm-level data from "Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS)". We assess the impact of adopting environment protection actions on the probability of integrating GVCs (extensive margin) and on the degree of participation (intensive margin) in GVCs.

The empirical findings support the role of environmental protection measures in boosting firms' participation in GVCs, through the mediation of productivity gains. Precisely, the adoption of environmental actions is likely to increase the firm's opportunity to integrate GVCs. This effect tends to be relatively higher for large corporates than for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). However, there is no significant evidence on the effect of the adoption of such actions on the intensity of engagement in GVCs. Indeed, green investments could be considered as an additional source of firm heterogeneity that can help firms overcome the sunk costs of internationalization. Therefore, based on the firm heterogeneity theory, the engagement in environmental activities is more likely to affect the extensive than the intensive margin of GVC integration. Our results remain robust after we control for the selection bias using a Heckman-2SLS approach.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: a review of the literature is displayed in the following section, followed by the data and stylized facts in section 3. Section 4 is dedicated the methodology, and section 5 analyzes the empirical results. The robustness checks are included in section 6 and section 7 concludes and provides some policy implications.

2. Literature Review

The interrelationship between international trade and environmental performance, whether at the macroeconomic level or at the microeconomic level, occupies a prominent position in the recent literature. Most of the studies tend to determine the impact of trade liberalization on the environment. However, the impact of environmental performance improvements on trade has received scant attention, especially when focusing on the firm level dynamics. Thus, to examine the impact of environmental performance on GVC participation, we bridge the gap between two strands of the literature: first, the firm-level determinants of participation in GVCs, and second, the environmental performance and its impact on firms' performance.

As the emergence and the expansion of GVCs have reshaped trade flows in the globalized world economy, the literature on international trade is no longer concerned with trade in final goods but rather focuses on trade in value added within global value chains (GVCs). Among the earliest empirical investigations revolving GVCs, Feenstra and Hanson (1996) define participation in GVCs (offshoring) by the amount of imported intermediate goods by an American firm relative to its total purchase of inputs for manufacturing industry through the period 1972 – 1994. Afterwards, a new strand in the literature has emerged to examine the theoretical and conceptual framework of the fragmentation of the production

process into particular tasks that are reallocated in different countries of the world (Baldwin, 2006 and Grossman and Rossi-Hansberg, 2008).

While different empirical studies on GVCs have arisen subsequently, they were at first dominated by macroeconomic cross-country analyses using input-output tables. Yet, the study of GVCs from a firm level perspective has gained significant attention at both the theoretical or empirical levels.

First, the theoretical framework, developed in order to examine firms' dynamics within GVCs, draws its basis from the work of Melitz (2003). The latter emphasizes the role of productivity heterogeneity in defining the patterns of trade; as the firm's decision to export is determined based on the sunk foreign market entry cost and the firm's level of productivity; allowing only the most productive firms to enter foreign markets. Antras and Helpman (2004) extend the heterogeneous firm model of Melitz (2003) to analyze firms' participation in GVCs. Their theoretical model suggests that among the productive firms that serve the foreign market, only the most productive ones succeed in engaging in foreign direct investment (FDI) by offshoring the production of some of their intermediate inputs or in foreign outsourcing⁴.

At the empirical level, most of the studies identify a firm as a participant in a GVC if it is a two-way trader; hence, it is simultaneously directly or indirectly exporting and importing intermediate inputs (Cieřlik et al., 2019 and Urata and Baek, 2020). However, Beghin et al. (2015), Nadvi (2008) and Prete (2017) consider each international trader; either exporter, importer or two-way trader, holding an internationally recognized quality certification, as a GVC firm. Then, a more comprehensive approach to identify firms who are integrated in GVCs has been developed by Dosis and Zaki (2020), which provides four different definitions of GVC firms. Firstly, the least strict definition considers that all two-way traders are involved in GVCs. The second definition includes two-way traders who hold an international quality certification and the third one includes two-way traders with foreign ownership. Lastly, the fourth and the strictest definition requires the reunion of these three criteria, as only two-way traders with an international quality certification and foreign ownership are considered as GVC firms.

The empirical literature shows that firm productivity is a fundamental determinant of its integration in a GVC. Indeed, firms, who have different levels of productivity, face a trade-off between incurring the variable transport cost of exporting to a foreign market and incurring the fixed cost of opening a foreign affiliate (offshoring). Yeaple (2009) argues that, for the U.S. multinational enterprises, only the most productive firms in the domestic market would bear to open foreign affiliates, yet less productive ones will find it more profitable to export. Additionally, further empirical investigations have defined, using cross-country firm-level data from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys, a set of firm characteristics as key determinants of participation in GVCs, which are high labor productivity, firm size, foreign ownership, high technological capabilities and the possession of international quality certification (Cieřlik et al., 2019 and Urata and Baek, 2020).

On another front, the relationship between environmental sustainability and firm's economic performance is attracting a growing attention, in the light of two main contradictory views, namely the Porter Hypothesis and the Pollution Haven Hypothesis (Porter and Linde, 1995, Ambec et al., 2013 and Gill, 2018). On the one hand, the latter suggests that strict environmental regulations in developed countries can lead firms to relocate their production to countries with weaker environmental regulations,

⁴ Antras and Helpman (2004) define foreign outsourcing as the purchase of inputs from a foreign supplier.

seeking the avoidance of the costs of complying with such regulations. In that case, the risk would be a « *race to the bottom* » as globalization necessitates a shift to lower environmental standards for countries to become more competitive and attract foreign direct investments (FDIs). On the other hand, The Porter Hypothesis, named after the economist Michael Porter, challenges this view, by emphasizing the role of environmental regulations in « *triggering innovation* », resulting in productivity gains that mitigate and sometimes counteract the cost of complying with these regulations. Firms would be able to achieve simultaneously environmental and economic upgrading. Therefore, the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) introduced the concept of eco-efficiency to reconcile the economic benefits with ecological improvements and thus increase the social and environmental responsibilities of firms (Muthu, 2020). In addition, based on the Porter hypothesis, firms' eco-efficiency can also lead to higher productivity levels (Boyd and McClelland, 1999 and Delmas and Pekovic, 2012). This is mainly related to the decrease in pollutant emissions by reducing the amount of waste, thus less inputs and higher outputs (Glavič et al., 2012) or a higher labor productivity (Berman and Bui, 2001 and Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2013). In other words, green strategies might not necessarily be associated to the conventional idea according to which environment-friendly investments (that are costly) lead to lower competitiveness (Antonietti and Marzucchi, 2013). In the same vein, other studies prove that the firm's efforts targeting its environmental performance can lead to a reduction in its production costs and enhance the efficiency of inputs' usage (Sheldon, 1997 and Christmann, 2000).

As per trade, GVC and the environment, Cui et al. (2012) develop a theoretical model to tackle the relationship between adopting clean technologies and exporting firms, by introducing a choice of technology upgrade to a cleaner one in the framework of Melitz (2003). They define three levels of productivity cutoffs and argue that less productive firms serve the domestic market while preserving their dirty technology, more productive firms succeed in entering the foreign market but also preserve their dirty technology and only the most productive firms can upgrade to a cleaner technology. However, under different assumptions regarding the cost structure, the results show that the productivity cutoff above which firms upgrade to a cleaner technology is lower than the productivity cutoff above which firms enter the foreign market. Nonetheless, the cutoff of clean technology remains higher than the one above which firms serve the domestic market without technology upgrading. At the empirical level, Galdeano-Gómez (2010) finds a 41% differential of environmental productivity between exporters and non-exporters. Moreover, Girma et al. (2008) and Cui et al. (2016) argue that the most productive firms – exporters – are more likely to bear the fixed investment cost of adopting a cleaner technology than non-exporters firms, who eventually have lower levels of productivity. On the other hand, the positive relationship between productivity and environmental performance may be also attributed to the efficiency of the production of more productive firms, who by definition manage to produce the same quantity of output, while using less inputs than less productive ones, thus emitting less pollution (Cui et al., 2016).

Nonetheless, studies examining the impact of firms' environmental upgrading on their performance on the international market are scarcer and lack a comprehensive cross-country analysis. For instance, Antonietti and Marzucchi (2013) show that, for the Italian manufacturing firms, firm's investments aiming at reducing the environmental impact of their production and the use of inputs are one of the sources of firm productivity heterogeneity, predicted by Melitz (2003). Therefore, green investments can have a significant positive indirect effect on firms export performance at both the extensive margin and the intensive margin through productivity gains. Similarly, further empirical investigations on the food industry show evidence of the positive impact of environmental performance on the intensity of exports of the firms (Alpay et al., 2001 and Galdeano-Gómez, 2010).

In a nutshell, the received literature shows that exporting firms tend to experience an environmental upgrading. However, the evidence on the positive effect of environmental performance on GVC integration has not been thoroughly studied. Therefore, this paper contributes to the existing literature by assessing the impact of firms' environmentally oriented investments on the likelihood of integrating GVCs and on the intensity of GVC participation for a sample of firms from developing and emerging countries.

3. Data and Stylized Facts

In our analysis, we rely on firm-level data for 41 countries from the “Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS)”⁵ (between 2018 and 2020). It includes cross-country data that cover almost 28,000 enterprises in 41 countries⁶ in 4 different regions, namely the European Union, Eastern Europe, Central Asia and Middle East and North Africa. The dataset comprises a large array of key characteristics, performance indicators and economic variables (i.e., total annual sales, volume of exports and imports, output, etc.) of firms with at least 5 full-time employees in both the manufacturing and the services sectors. Moreover, the sixth round of BEEPS (BEEPS 18-20) includes a Green Economy module that comprises questions about the green investments and the environmental actions adopted by the firms. As the BEEPS 18-20 is the first BEEPS to include questions about firms' environmental actions, the application of a panel analysis is not possible since the analysis is restricted to the cross-sectional data

Global Value Chain (GVC) firms are distinguished by their involvement in the production and distribution of goods and services across different stages and locations around the world. They are usually highly specialized, focusing on a particular product or stage of the production process of the GVC in which they participate (World Bank, 2023). The existing literature also deduces that GVC firms tend to be larger, more productive, foreign-owned and have internationally recognized quality certification (Cieřlik et al., 2019 and Urata and Baek, 2020). As it was mentioned before, to define GVC, we follow Dervis and Zaki (2020). The first definition (GVC 1) is the laxest one as it considers all two-way traders, hence firms simultaneously exporting and importing, as GVC firms. The second (GVC 2) includes two-way traders who hold an international quality certification and the third (GVC 3) includes two-way traders with foreign ownership⁷. Finally, the strictest definition (GVC 4) entails exclusively two-way traders with foreign ownership who hold an international quality certification⁸. While these variables measure GVC at the extensive margin, we follow (Urata and Baek, 2020) to measure GVC at the intensive level. The latter is the share of the firm's exports multiplied by the share of its imported inputs.

Table 1 shows the share of GVC firms, according to each definition, across the different regions, highlighting that the higher share of GVC firms is in the European Union. The share of GVC firms, defined according to the strictest definition (GVC 4) is only 2.5% among all firms in our dataset.

⁵ These surveys are conducted jointly by World Bank, the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)

⁶ The list of countries and years is displayed in Appendix Table [A1](#).

⁷ Foreign ownership is defined based on whether the share of foreign ownership is greater than 10% or not (a foreign direct investment).

⁸ See Table A1 for the distribution of firms by region according to their different characteristics. Generally, most of the firms in the sample (77%) are domestic, with the highest share of domestic firms in Central Asia. Moreover, a large proportion of the firms import foreign intermediate inputs, especially firms in Eastern Europe

Table 1: Distribution of GVC firms by region (%)

	GVC 1	GVC 2	GVC 3	GVC 4
European Union	31.9	17.6	6.8	4.5
Eastern Europe	24.8	10.1	4.2	1.9
MENA Region	17.6	7.6	3.9	1.6
Central Asia	12.9	5.4	2.4	1.1
All	22.9	10.9	4.6	2.5

Source: Authors' own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

The data in this sample matches the literature that argues that GVC firms tend to be large corporations rather than small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Cieřlik et al., 2019 and Urata and Baek, 2020). Indeed, Figure 1 shows that the share of GVC firms, among the small-sized firms, is only 13% and is the highest for the larger ones, as it reaches 40%. In addition, Figure 2 confirms this fact given that large firms are involved in GVCs at the intensive margin level.

Figure 1: Share of domestic firms versus GVC firms, by firm size

Source: Authors' own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

Figure 2: Distribution of the GVC Participation Index, by firm size

Source: Authors' own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

Global Value Chains are most prevalent in manufacturing industries (Wang et al., 2023). Indeed, manufacturing sectors as machinery, equipment, electronics, and vehicles embody a large share of GVC firms compared to domestic firms at both the extensive (Figure 3) and the intensive (Figure 4) margin levels. This is in line with Rodrik (2018) who argues that high-tech and knowledge intensive sectors rely heavily on global value chains. However, sectors such as the construction sector and the industry of leather products show a low share of GVC firms.

Figure 3: Share of domestic firms versus GVC firms, by sector

Source: Authors’ own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

Figure 4: Distribution of the GVC Participation Index, by sector

Source: Authors’ own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

When it comes to environmental and ecological measures, the evaluation of the firm’s environmental performance, is based on its engagement in different environmental actions, namely adopting an eco-friendly energy generation, energy management measures, any measures that enhance energy efficiency, air pollution control measures, water management measures or waste minimization, recycling, and waste management measures. Figure 5 compares the average level of productivity between firms who adopt one of these environmental actions and those who do not. In line with the received literature, the average level of productivity of firms engaged in environmental actions (except for adopting an eco-friendly energy generation) is generally higher than the average level of firms who do not adopt such measures (Delmas and Pekovic, 2012 and Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2013).

Figure 5: Average level of productivity and adoption of environment friendly measures

Source: Authors’ own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

As environmental activities are associated with higher productivity levels, it is expected that firms who engage more in such actions are more productive and hence get access to the international market, as affirmed by Melitz (2003). Correspondingly, Figure 6 shows that the share of GVC firms, among those who adopt environmental actions, is higher than the corresponding share of domestic firms. Hence, GVC firms tend to have a higher environmental performance (Girma et al., 2008 and Cui et al., 2016). Nevertheless, Figure 7 does not show noticeable evidence of a positive association between environmental upgrading and the intensity of participation in GVCs. Therefore, environmental performance may be affecting the probability of integration in GVCs rather than the intensity of GVC participation.

Figure 6: Share of domestic firms versus GVC firms among

Source: Authors' own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

Figure 7: GVC Participation Index and adoption of environmental measures

Source: Author's own elaboration using BEEPS data for 2018 – 2020.

In a nutshell, this descriptive analysis shows that there is an association between firm's environmentally oriented investments and their level of productivity and their potential participation in GVCs (more than the intensity of their participation in GVCs). This confirms the fact that such measures are perceived as a fixed cost that affects the extensive margin of GVC more than a variable cost that affects the intensive margin.

4. Methodology

In this paper, we attempt to assess the impact of the firm's environmental performance on GVC integration at both the intensive and the extensive levels. That is done within the theoretical framework of the heterogeneous firm model that accounts for the role of the heterogeneity of the firms' characteristics in terms of their productivity levels, inputs, technology, and other features in determining their behavior on the international market (Melitz, 2003 and Cieřlik et al., 2019).

We focus on two dependent variables. The first is measuring the likelihood for a firm to participate in a GVC (extensive margin), by a dummy variable that takes the value 1 if the firm (i) in industry (j) of country I in year (t) is a part of a GVC and 0 otherwise. To account for the various definitions of GVC firms elaborated by DAVIS and ZAKI (2020), the regression is estimated for each of the four definitions separately, using the linear probability model. The second one measures the degree of participation of firm (i) in industry (j) of country (c) in year (t) in GVCs, using a GVC index that is computed for each firm, following Urata and Baek (2020):

$$GVC\ Index = \left(\frac{Exports}{Total\ Sales} \right) * \left(\frac{Imported\ inputs}{Total\ procurements} \right) \quad (1)$$

The specifications of the empirical model are defined based on the existing literature on the fundamental firm-level determinants of integration in GVCs as follows:

$$GVC_{i,j,c,t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{i,j,c,t} + \beta_2 EP_{i,j,c,t} + \delta_j + \delta_c + \delta_t + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

Where ($X_{i,j,c,t}$) is a vector of control variables that includes firms' characteristics that affect the firms' participation in GVCs as; firm size, firm age, and foreign ownership (Cieřlik et al., 2019 and Urata and Baek, 2020). The firm size is captured by dummy variables, who subdivide firms into 3 categories, namely *small size* (firms with 5 – 20 employees), *medium size* (firms with 20 – 99 employees) and *large size* (firms with more than 99 employees). The *firm age* is calculated by taking the natural logarithm of the difference between the year when the survey was conducted for the firm and the year in which the firm has started its operations. The *foreign ownership* is included as the natural logarithm of the share of capital owned by foreigners. (δ_j , δ_c and δ_t) represent industry, country, and year fixed effects, respectively and (ε) is an error term.

The main variable of interest ($EP_{i,j,c,t}$) measures the firm's environmental performance through a vector of six dummy variables; each representing an environmental action, that takes the value 1 if the firm is adopting this action and 0 otherwise. The environmental actions are divided into three dimensions, following Dangelico and Pontrandolfo (2013). Firstly, environmental actions related to raw materials usage include the adoption of waste minimization, recycling and waste management and the adoption of water management. Secondly, actions related to energy usage include the adoption of more climate-friendly energy generation on site, the adoption of energy management and the adoption of any measures to enhance energy efficiency. Finally, actions related to pollution are represented by the adoption of air pollution control measures.

Obviously, this equation suffers from a selection bias given that firms are not observed at the intensive margin level of GVC unless they are already observed at the extensive margin one. This is why we adopt a two-stage Heckman selection model. The first stage is estimated to define the determinants of integration into GVCs, while the second determines the variables that affect the intensity of participation in GVCs. Our selection variable is the export intensity of the geographical region of the firm ($Exp Intensity_{i,j,c,t}$). It is computed as the natural logarithm of the value of exports of the geographical region in which the firm is located divided by the average value of exports in the country. The export intensity of the region is expected to affect the likelihood of integrating GVCs (extensive margin) as firms located in export intensive regions should get easier access to international market and should benefit from the exchange of information regarding international opportunities, competitors, and partners, the presence of local expertise and good quality institutions and the support from the existing public agencies in the region. However, the export intensity of the region should not affect the degree of participation in GVCs (intensive margin), which depends more on the firm's own characteristics (Antonietti and Marzucchi, 2013).

Second, as the regressions suffer from a potential endogeneity, because of the presence of a reverse causality between participation in GVCs and firms' environmental performance as proven by the literature; exporters are more likely to adopt green investments than non-exporters (Girma et al., 2008 and Cui et al., 2016), it would be more appropriate to interpret the estimated results as correlations between environmental performance and GVC integration. Moreover, the absence of a panel dimension in the data does not allow us to control for firm fixed effects (Urata and Baek, 2020). However, to partially address this issue, a shift-share instrument is used (Ferri, 2022). Thus, the firm's environmental performance is instrumented by the shift-share instrument, which is computed as the industry-country-year average (calculated for all firms of a certain country in a specific industry and for the same year) minus the firm's own response (Dovis and Zaki, 2020).

Thus, we adopt the Heckman – 2SLS approach, which is commonly used to address endogeneity problems in cross-sectional data. The advantage of the Heckman – 2SLS model is that it allows to correct for both the sample selection bias and the endogeneity bias by combining the Heckman selection model as the first stage and the two-stage least squares regression as the second stage (Liu et al., 2021). In other words, it consists of estimating a first stage Probit model that examines the likelihood of integrating a GVC, including the shift-share instrument and the selection variable (export intensity of the geographical region of the firm). Then, from this Probit regression the probability of sample selection (inverse of mills ratio (IMR)) is predicted. Finally, a 2SLS regression is carried out in the second stage, while incorporating the probability of selection (IMR) as an additional variable to account for the selection bias and instrumenting the endogenous explanatory variable by the shift-share instrument to control the endogeneity bias.

Our analysis is extended by examining the heterogeneity stemming from firm size. This will help us examine the potential differences in the impact of green investments on the likelihood of integrating GVCs between small, medium, and large who have different capabilities, resources, and constraints.

5. Empirical Findings

For the sake of brevity, this section reports the results of the first definition of GVC for firms who are two-way traders (directly or indirectly exporting and importing)⁹. Table 3 reports the results of the baseline model. Then, the impact of the firms' environmental performance on the likelihood of participating in GVCs and on the degree of participation in GVCs is reported in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. Table 6 addresses the heterogeneity of this impact on firms with various sizes. Lastly, Table 7 and 8 show the results of the Heckman two-stage selection model and the Heckman – 2SLS model, respectively.

First, the baseline model results (Table 3) display the fundamental determinants of integration into GVCs (extensive margin) and the firms' key characteristics that affect the intensity of GVC participation. Despite that the firm's age exert a positive significant effect on the extensive margin as expected, its coefficient becomes negative for the intensive margin (*GVC Index*). This result is in line with previous studies in the literature that show that older firms are more likely to integrate GVCs owing to their experience rather than younger ones, but as the latter are assumed to be more innovative, they tend to have a higher degree of GVC participation (Urata and Baek, 2020 and Karam and Zaki, 2021). The foreign ownership has a positive and significant impact on the GVC index. However, it was not possible to examine its impact on the probability of integrating GVCs, as foreign ownership represents one of the firms' key characteristics used in the definitions of GVC firms (definitions 3 and 4). It is noteworthy that the export intensity of the geographical region in which the firm is located within the country affects positively and exclusively the extensive margin without impacting the intensive margin as predicted by Antonietti and Marzucchi (2013). Therefore, as it will be shown later, it represents an adequate selection variable to run the Heckman two-stage selection model and the Heckman – 2SLS model.

Second, for firm's environmental performance, we regress environmental action variables individually given their potential collinearity.¹⁰ The results in Table 4 highlight that the improvement of the environmental performance of the firm, illustrated by the adoption of an environmental action, increases the probability of its integration in GVCs (extensive margin)¹¹. Notably, adopting measures that tend to reduce the emitted air pollutants by the firm has the highest impact as it increases the firm's chance to integrate a GVC by 9.4%. The results apply to the adoption of an energy management plan, waste minimization, reduction of air pollution, water management, and energy efficiency measures. The results of waste management are particularly important as it helps reducing the amount of materials that are used in the production of goods and services, which leads to a decline in the amount of waste generated is also reduced and thus less energy is required to process the waste. Moreover, energy efficiency measures and management plans enhance production and capacity utilization, reduce resource use and pollution, and lower operation costs. For instance, the experience of Schneider Electric sites that adopted the Superior Energy Performance (SEP) Program experienced an increase in energy savings by 7.5% compared to 3.2% before certification (IAE, 2018).

⁹ See the Appendix Table A2, A3 and A4 for the results of other GVC definitions.

¹⁰ See the Appendix Table A5 for the results of the regression incorporating all the environmental actions variables together.

¹¹ The baseline regression is re-estimated using a Probit model, since it captures the non-linear relationships between the independent variables and the outcome variable. The results in Table A5 are in line with the positive and significant effect of environmental performance on the extensive margin reported in Table 4.

In contrast, the GVC firms' engagement in environmental activities does not affect the intensity of their participation in GVCs (intensive margin), as shown in Table 5. This finding is in line with the New-New Trade literature, as the environmental performance is expected to affect the integration in GVCs through the channel of productivity given that firms adopting cleaner technologies tend to experience productivity gains (Girma et al., 2008 and Delmas and Pekovic, 2012). The heterogeneous firm model emphasizes the role of the firm's level of productivity in determining its participation on the international market, thus in GVCs (Melitz, 2003 and Cieřlik et al., 2019). Therefore, investments in cleaner production technologies could be considered as an additional source of fixed costs and thus of firm heterogeneity. These costs include the adoption of such green investments that require the reshaping of the production organization; training employees to adapt to these new technologies; reducing waste and pollution; and adopting new business models and strategies to align with the environmental goals (Hart and Ahuja, 1996). Finally, it is also worth noting that the benefits of green investments may not be realized immediately, as it may take time to achieve the expected productivity gains and cost savings (Elsayed and Paton, 2005). It is important to note that these conclusions may not seem fully consistent with the existing literature which argues that environmental performance affects the firm's export performance at both the extensive and the intensive margins (Alpay et al., 2001, Galdeano-Gómez, 2010 and Antonietti and Marzucchi, 2013). Nevertheless, it should be recalled that these estimates may be biased due to the two-way causality problem and the selection bias that will be addressed later.

The effects of environmental measures adoption are heterogenous. Table 6 shows that the impact of the firm's environmental performance on the likelihood of integrating GVCs is conditional on the firm's size. Despite the positive and significant impact of environmental actions on the performance of firms of various sizes, it is worth noting that, when the firm's size is interacted with environmental performance variables, that higher positive coefficients are associated with larger firms. This suggests that larger firms are more likely to experience an international upgrading, regarding their participation in GVCs, through the adoption of green investments, compared to their smaller counterparts. This could be due to the fact that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) face resources constraints and limited access to financing, which makes it challenging for them to invest in new clean technologies. In addition, they may also struggle to attract skilled labor due to their inability to offer competitive wages, which may stifle the productivity gains attained through such investments. (El-Said et al., 2015 and Urata and Baek, 2020). The literature has indeed shown that larger (that are more productive) firms are more likely to incur high fixed costs that could potentially include the cost of adopting such measures.

In order to address the selection bias in the regression that examines the degree of participation in GVCs (intensive margin), a Heckman two-stage selection model is estimated, using the export intensity of the geographical region in which the firm is located within the country as the selection variable. Recall that Table 3 shows that this variable only affects the extensive margin and not the intensity of participation in GVCs. The Heckman selection model (Table 7) reinforces the previous results, by emphasizing the positive effect of adopting environmental actions on the extensive margin, while the effect on the intensive margin persists to be weaker or insignificant in most of the cases, confirming that such measures are perceived as a fixed cost that requires non-negligible amounts of investments.

After controlling for the selection bias, our results might still suffer from an endogeneity problem given that firms that are part of GVC (and thus more exposed to international competition) might be more likely to adopt such environmental measures. This is why the final stage of our analysis comprises treating the problem of endogeneity and the selection bias simultaneously, by estimating a Heckman – 2SLS model

with shift-share instruments. The results shown in Table 8 are also in line with the previous conclusions, showing a positive and significant impact of environmentally oriented investments on the likelihood of integrating a GVC and a negligible effect on the intensity of participation in GVCs.

In sum, the formerly reported results show that firms, who pursue environmental upgrading by adopting new measures to control their environmental impact, experience a performance upgrading reflected by a higher chance to integrate GVCs owing to productivity gains. However, this effect tends to be relatively higher for large firms compared to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Finally, the adoption of green investments by GVC firms may not necessarily lead to a significant increase in the intensity of their involvement in GVCs. Overall, the consistency of the results across different models and definitions provides stronger evidence in support of the relationship between environmental performance and GVC integration.

Table 3: Baseline Regression

	Prob(GVC)	GVC Index
Firm Age	0.0155*** (0.00329)	-0.122** (0.0528)
Export intensity	0.0612*** (0.00339)	0.0986 (0.0794)
Foreign ownership		0.316*** (0.0474)
Constant	0.394*** (0.0253)	3.131*** (0.423)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes
Observations	27,389	1,215
R-squared	0.206	0.312

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 4: Impact of environmental performance on the likelihood of GVC

	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)
Firm Age	0.0134*** (0.00333)	0.0123*** (0.00332)	0.0134*** (0.00332)	0.0127*** (0.00332)	0.0133*** (0.00332)	0.0123*** (0.00336)
Export intensity	0.0607*** (0.00341)	0.0603*** (0.00340)	0.0581*** (0.00341)	0.0601*** (0.00341)	0.0604*** (0.00341)	0.0619*** (0.00343)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0879*** (0.00727)					
Energy management		0.0810*** (0.00530)				
Waste minimization			0.0812*** (0.00519)			
Air pollution				0.0940*** (0.00689)		
Water management					0.0693*** (0.00610)	
Energy efficiency						0.0760*** (0.00526)
Constant	0.392*** (0.0255)	0.376*** (0.0255)	0.379*** (0.0256)	0.385*** (0.0256)	0.387*** (0.0255)	0.397*** (0.0257)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094
R-squared	0.211	0.213	0.214	0.212	0.211	0.211

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 5: Impact of environmental performance on the degree of participation in GVCs

	GVC Index					
Firm Age	-0.115** (0.0538)	-0.117** (0.0538)	-0.118** (0.0535)	-0.119** (0.0537)	-0.115** (0.0536)	-0.115** (0.0542)
Foreign ownership	0.321*** (0.0483)	0.319*** (0.0484)	0.328*** (0.0484)	0.320*** (0.0482)	0.320*** (0.0483)	0.318*** (0.0488)
Export intensity	0.0951 (0.0809)	0.0905 (0.0813)	0.0946 (0.0804)	0.0973 (0.0809)	0.0885 (0.0808)	0.0901 (0.0815)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0161 (0.0912)					
Energy management		-0.00469 (0.0757)				
Waste minimization			0.0487 (0.0784)			
Air pollution				0.0551 (0.0813)		
Water management					-0.0849 (0.0801)	
Energy efficiency						0.0142 (0.0781)
Constant	3.053*** (0.428)	3.069*** (0.430)	3.011*** (0.431)	3.061*** (0.431)	3.045*** (0.431)	3.040*** (0.433)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,187	1,184	1,189	1,181	1,184	1,162
R-squared	0.312	0.312	0.313	0.312	0.314	0.309

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 6: Impact of the interactions between environmental performance and firm size on the likelihood of GVC integration

	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)	Prob(GVC)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0556*** (0.0126)					
Eco -friendly Energy * Medium	0.0161 (0.0173)					
Eco -friendly Energy * Large	0.0811*** (0.0176)					
Energy management		0.0387*** (0.00824)				
Energy management * Medium		0.0394*** (0.0119)				
Energy management * Large		0.110*** (0.0129)				
Waste minimization			0.0286*** (0.00764)			
Waste minimization * Medium			0.0620*** (0.0112)			
Waste minimization * Large			0.133*** (0.0124)			
Air pollution				0.0475*** (0.0120)		
Air pollution * Medium				0.0326** (0.0164)		
Air pollution * Large				0.103*** (0.0165)		
Water management					0.0288*** (0.00988)	
Water management * Medium					0.0292** (0.0139)	
Water management * Large					0.102*** (0.0145)	
Energy efficiency						0.0393*** (0.00797)
Energy efficiency * Medium						0.0331*** (0.0117)
Energy efficiency * Large						0.103*** (0.0128)
Constant	0.395*** (0.0256)	0.389*** (0.0255)	0.395*** (0.0256)	0.391*** (0.0256)	0.395*** (0.0255)	0.411*** (0.0258)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094
R-squared	0.212	0.215	0.217	0.213	0.212	0.213

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 7: Empirical Results - Heckman Selection Model

	Prob (GVC) (1 st stage)	GVC Index (2 nd stage)	Obs.
(1) Eco -friendly Energy	0.297*** (0.0838)	0.118 (0.105)	26,615
(2) Energy management	0.352*** (0.0676)	0.156 (0.0993)	26,611
(3) Waste minimization	0.312*** (0.0674)	0.208** (0.1)	26,655
(4) Air pollution	0.303*** (0.0756)	0.193* (0.101)	26,587
(5) Water management	0.266*** (0.0726)	0.0354 (0.0963)	26,623
(6) Energy efficiency	0.288*** (0.0676)	0.144 (0.0943)	26,094

Each row represents an individual regression.

Country, sector, size and year dummies are included in all regressions.

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 8: Empirical Results– Heckman 2SLS approach.

	Prob (GVC) (1 st stage)	GVC Index (2 nd stage)	Obs.
(1) Eco -friendly Energy	2.177*** (0.223)	1.525* (0.846)	26,595
(2) Energy management	1.759*** (0.135)	1.552 (1.250)	26,589
(3) Waste minimization	1.778*** (0.116)	-2.853 (9.295)	26,633
(4) Air pollution	2.234*** (0.170)	5.292 (3.560)	26,565
(5) Water management	1.280*** (0.279)	0.604 (1.101)	26,601
(6) Energy efficiency	1.053*** (0.303)	1.712** (0.730)	26,072

Each row represents an individual regression.

Country, sector, size and year dummies are included in all regressions.

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

6. Conclusion and Policy Implications

The paper assesses the impact of firms' adoption of environment protection actions on the likelihood of participating in GVCs (extensive margin) and the degree of GVC participation (intensive margin), using the Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS) that comprises firm-level data from 41 countries. The main findings of the paper suggest that the adoption of environment protection actions boosts the firm's opportunity to integrate GVCs, owing to productivity gains. However, the results do not provide evidence on the impact of such activities on the intensity of participation of GVC firms. Therefore, investments in cleaner production technologies could be considered as fixed cost. Hence, they tend to matter more for entering GVCs rather than for intensifying the participation of integrated firms. When firm size is taken into account, large corporates are more likely to benefit from investing in environmental activities rather than smaller firms, which suffer to get access to financing resources and skilled labor. The latter finding is certainly crucial for the definition of tailored recommendations suitable to the specific needs of different firms to promote their successful integration into GVC and to reach the net zero emissions target.

From a policy perspective, major and significant environmental challenges that threaten sustainable development have forced the elaboration of multiple national and international environmental policies and regulations, though few significant positive outcomes have been achieved in terms of sustainable development (Cui et al., 2016). Therefore, this study provides evidence on the implications of firms' adoption of environmental policies and regulations to be more and better integrated in GVCs. Thus, governments need to provide incentives for firms to comply with environmental regulations, given that the adoption of clean technologies is usually associated with significant costs and requires the reshaping of the production organization. This can take place through adequate public investments, notably in green infrastructure that raises the firms' private benefits and through technical and financial support to firms investing in sustainable practices. As predicted by Porter and Linde (1995), the elaboration of well-designed environmental regulations should result in productivity gains owing to the firms' investments in clean and innovative technologies, which may partially, sometimes fully or more than fully « *offset* » the initial costs of complying to the regulations. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the relationship between green investments and GVCs intensity is complex and context-specific given that there may be other factors that mediate this relationship. Indeed, upgrading within GVCs involves a complex combination of factors, including access to technology, skills, and financing (Urata and Baek, 2020), thus the adoption of green investments may not be a sufficient condition for upgrading within GVCs. In addition, the effect of green investments on the intensity of participation in GVCs may differ depending on the context and the characteristics of the GVC in which the firm is involved. For instance, Antonietti and Marzucchi (2013) argue that the impact of such environmental upgrading on firms' performance on the international market tends to be higher for firms who export to markets with stricter environmental regulations.

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Appendices

Table A1: List of sample countries and years of the BEEPS (2018-2020).

Albania (2018, 2019)	Italy (2018, 2019)	Poland (2019)
Armenia (2019, 2020)	Jordan (2019)	Portugal (2018, 2019, 2020)
Azerbaijan (2019, 2020)	Kazakhstan (2019)	Romania (2018, 2019, 2020)
Belarus (2018, 2019)	Kosovo (2018, 2019)	Russia (2018, 2019)
Bosnia and Herzegovina (2019)	Kyrgyz Republic (2018, 2019)	Serbia (2018, 2019)
Bulgaria (2019, 2020)	Latvia (2018, 2019)	Slovak Republic (2019, 2020)
Croatia (2018, 2019)	Lebanon (2019, 2020)	Slovenia (2018, 2019)
Cyprus (2018, 2019)	Lithuania (2018, 2019)	Tajikistan (2019)
Czech Republic (2018, 2019, 2020)	Malta (2019)	Tunisia (2019, 2020)
Egypt (2019, 2020)	Moldova (2019)	Turkey (2018, 2019)
Estonia (2018, 2019)	Mongolia (2018, 2019)	Ukraine (2018, 2019)
Georgia (2019, 2020)	Montenegro (2018, 2019)	Uzbekistan (2019)
Greece (2018, 2019)	Morocco (2018, 2019, 2020)	West Bank and Gaza (2019)
Hungary (2018, 2019, 2020)	North Macedonia (2018, 2019)	

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Table A2: Impact of environmental performance on the likelihood of integrating GVC2.

	GVC 2					
Firm Age	0.0224*** (0.00252)	0.0209*** (0.00251)	0.0222*** (0.00251)	0.0210*** (0.00251)	0.0213*** (0.00251)	0.0209*** (0.00253)
Export intensity	0.0183*** (0.00258)	0.0179*** (0.00257)	0.0162*** (0.00258)	0.0174*** (0.00257)	0.0178*** (0.00257)	0.0184*** (0.00258)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0690*** (0.00550)					
Energy management		0.0773*** (0.00400)				
Waste minimization			0.0706*** (0.00393)			
Air pollution				0.0993*** (0.00520)		
Water management					0.0811*** (0.00460)	
Energy efficiency						0.0696*** (0.00396)
Constant	0.0969*** (0.0193)	0.0799*** (0.0193)	0.0863*** (0.0194)	0.0878*** (0.0193)	0.0907*** (0.0193)	0.0930*** (0.0194)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094
R-squared	0.186	0.192	0.191	0.192	0.190	0.190

Standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A3: Impact of environmental performance on the likelihood of integrating GVC3.

	GVC 3					
Firm Age	-0.0127*** (0.00178)	-0.0129*** (0.00178)	-0.0123*** (0.00178)	-0.0128*** (0.00177)	-0.0126*** (0.00177)	-0.0129*** (0.00180)
Export intensity	0.0113*** (0.00182)	0.0111*** (0.00182)	0.0106*** (0.00183)	0.0108*** (0.00182)	0.0110*** (0.00182)	0.0111*** (0.00183)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0222*** (0.00389)					
Energy management		0.0234*** (0.00283)				
Waste minimization			0.0174*** (0.00278)			
Air pollution				0.0313*** (0.00368)		
Water management					0.0242*** (0.00326)	
Energy efficiency						0.0193*** (0.00281)
Constant	0.114*** (0.0137)	0.108*** (0.0136)	0.108*** (0.0137)	0.108*** (0.0136)	0.108*** (0.0136)	0.115*** (0.0137)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094
R-squared	0.211	0.213	0.214	0.212	0.211	0.211

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A4: Impact of environmental performance on the likelihood of integrating GVC 4.

	GVC 4	GVC 4	GVC 4	GVC 4	GVC 4	GVC 4
Firm Age	-0.00275** (0.00135)	-0.00302** (0.00135)	-0.00260* (0.00135)	-0.00309** (0.00135)	-0.00290** (0.00135)	-0.00279** (0.00136)
Export intensity	0.00378*** (0.00139)	0.00364*** (0.00138)	0.00324** (0.00139)	0.00352** (0.00138)	0.00367*** (0.00138)	0.00389*** (0.00139)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0185*** (0.00296)					
Energy management		0.0210*** (0.00215)				
Waste minimization			0.0157*** (0.00212)			
Air pollution				0.0320*** (0.00279)		
Water management					0.0231*** (0.00248)	
Energy efficiency						0.0178*** (0.00213)
Constant	0.0312*** (0.0104)	0.0264** (0.0104)	0.0285*** (0.0104)	0.0274*** (0.0104)	0.0286*** (0.0104)	0.0285*** (0.0104)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094
R-squared	0.071	0.073	0.072	0.074	0.073	0.073

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A5: Impact of environmental performance and on the degree of participation in GVCs.

	GVC 1	GVC 2	GVC 3	GVC 4	GVC Index
Firm Age	0.0101*** (0.00339)	0.0185*** (0.00254)	-0.0133*** (0.00181)	-0.00344** (0.00137)	-0.117** (0.0554)
Export intensity	0.0588*** (0.00345)	0.0166*** (0.00259)	0.0104*** (0.00185)	0.00342** (0.00140)	0.0719 (0.0835)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.0400*** (0.00807)	0.0156** (0.00606)	0.00861** (0.00431)	0.00425 (0.00327)	0.0226 (0.104)
Energy management	0.0292*** (0.00670)	0.0271*** (0.00502)	0.00858** (0.00358)	0.00711*** (0.00272)	-0.0212 (0.0950)
Waste minimization	0.0361*** (0.00604)	0.0304*** (0.00453)	0.00732** (0.00323)	0.00691*** (0.00245)	0.0245 (0.0922)
Air pollution	0.0432*** (0.00596)	0.0285*** (0.00447)	0.00376 (0.00318)	0.00225 (0.00242)	0.0477 (0.0927)
Water management	0.0373*** (0.00802)	0.0490*** (0.00602)	0.0179*** (0.00428)	0.0213*** (0.00325)	0.111 (0.0981)
Energy efficiency	0.00449 (0.00734)	0.0265*** (0.00551)	0.00758* (0.00392)	0.00773*** (0.00298)	-0.152 (0.0981)
Foreign ownership					0.306*** (0.0499)
Constant	0.363*** (0.0259)	0.0645*** (0.0194)	0.102*** (0.0138)	0.0203* (0.0105)	3.096*** (0.445)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	25,454	25,454	25,454	25,454	1,129
R-squared	0.218	0.202	0.093	0.076	0.311

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table A6: Impact of environmental performance on the likelihood of GVC integration - Probit model.

	GVC 1					
Firm Age	0.0551*** (0.0141)	0.0514*** (0.0141)	0.0550*** (0.0141)	0.0535*** (0.0141)	0.0562*** (0.0141)	0.0509*** (0.0142)
Export intensity	0.291*** (0.0163)	0.290*** (0.0164)	0.277*** (0.0163)	0.288*** (0.0163)	0.290*** (0.0163)	0.299*** (0.0165)
Eco -friendly Energy	0.299*** (0.0275)					
Energy management		0.295*** (0.0210)				
Waste minimization			0.301*** (0.0204)			
Air pollution				0.311*** (0.0262)		
Water management					0.253*** (0.0240)	
Energy efficiency						0.285*** (0.0209)
Constant	-0.322*** (0.0971)	-0.380*** (0.0974)	-0.377*** (0.0976)	-0.346*** (0.0974)	-0.343*** (0.0972)	-0.310*** (0.0978)
Size dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sector dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year dummies	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	26,615	26,611	26,655	26,587	26,623	26,094

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1